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Influence of Employee Satisfaction on Business Performance A Case Study of Cameroon

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of employee satisfaction on business performance in Cameroon, offering a detailed analysis of the factors that influence employee satisfaction and their subsequent effects on business success. The study employed a questionnaire-based method for data collection. Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) and Grey Relation Analysis (GRA) were used to investigate the how business performance is related to various factors through employee satisfaction. The results show that workplace environment, job security, and career advancement opportunities exhibit strong positive correlations with business outcomes, indicating significant relationship existing between them. Based on the GRA analysis, training and development were found to have high impact on business success. In practical terms, the study suggests that institutions in Cameroon should prioritize improving key aspects of employee satisfaction that have the most substantial effect on business performance. Enhancing workplace conditions while fostering career advancement can also boost employee morale and productivity. The findings of this study offer valuable insights for businesses and policymakers in Cameroon, emphasizing the importance of a strategic and balanced approach to employee satisfaction.

Keywords: Business performance; Satisfaction; Regression analysis; Cameroon**Introduction**

In response to the increasing market competition in recent years, many industries have been actively seeking ways to add value to their services and enhance service quality. With the rapid evolution of global markets and customer expectations, businesses find themselves under constant pressure to remain competitive (Soewarno et al., 2020). As a result, industries are not only looking to optimize their product offerings but also focusing on improving internal processes to better meet customer demands. In this regard, industries are increasingly recognizing operational efficiency as a critical factor in ensuring sustainability and long-term growth of their businesses. In particular, operations management (OM) has emerged as a key discipline, emphasizing the optimization of operational processes as a means to deliver value to customers' expectations (Handoyo et al., 2023). OM focuses on the design, execution, and control of operational processes within companies (Wolniak, 2020). The goal of OM is to enhance productivity, reduce waste, and ensure that products or services are delivered in the most efficient and cost-effective manner possible. By optimizing the use of resources, improving process flow, and ensuring smooth interactions between various business functions, OM enables companies to provide better value propositions to customers. Consequently, OM has become an essential discipline for businesses, especially in highly competitive markets where cost control, speed, and quality are paramount.

A number of studies has been conducted on topics related to designing, managing, and optimizing service delivery systems, with a view to enhancing profitability and productivity of companies while meeting employee needs (Frei et al., 1999; Soteriou and Zenios, 1999; Saccania et al., 2007). These studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of operations-centric approaches in achieving companies' performance. Human resources, which encompass employees' skills, attitudes, and behaviors, play a pivotal role in the effectiveness of a company's operations (Jing, 2018; Bjaalid et al., 2020; Gazi et al., 2023). While operations management has focused on optimizing processes, the impact of employee attitudes, such as job satisfaction, employee loyalty, and company commitment, on operational performance has often been neglected (Boudreau et al., 2003). These employee attributes, which directly influence job performance and overall productivity, are critical in service-oriented industries where the quality of service delivery is largely determined by the employees who interact with customers (Hsieh, 2016). For example, a service employee's attitude, communication skills, and commitment to customer satisfaction can significantly impact the customer's experience and their perception of the company (Gazi et al., 2024). Yet, the relationship between employee satisfaction and operational performance remains largely unexplored in traditional OM research. The disconnect between OM and human resources is particularly evident in the way these two fields have developed in parallel without much interaction. While OM focuses on optimizing processes and systems, human resources have concentrated on managing people, with particular emphasis on recruitment, training, and retention. However, as Boudreau et al. (2003) point out, this separation between OM and HR has resulted in an incomplete understanding of how human capital influences operational outcomes. Although human resources and operations are inherently intertwined in almost all business scenarios, the direct impact of employee attributes on operational systems have been largely overlooked in the academic literature. This gap in understanding has limited the ability of companies to fully leverage the potential of their workforce to drive operational success. The importance of employee attributes, such as job satisfaction, company commitment, and loyalty, has been well-established in fields such as psychology and organizational behavior, which have explored how these factors contribute to employee motivation, morale, and job performance (Vroom, 1964; Schwab and Cummings, 1970). A vast body of research has examined the relationship between employee attitudes and companies' outcomes, highlighting the critical role that employee satisfaction plays in determining the success of a business. For instance, studies have shown that satisfied employees are more likely to be engaged, productive, and committed to their work, which in turn enhances the quality of service provided to customers (Becker et al., 1996; Meyer et al., 2004). However, this research has not been integrated sufficiently into operations management theory, despite the fact that the quality of service and the efficiency of operational processes in service-oriented industries are heavily dependent on the performance of service employees. Despite the growing recognition of the importance of human resources in operational systems, there remains a lack of research that explicitly examines the intersection between employee satisfaction and business success. Employee satisfaction is among the key elements for the success of service-oriented operations and therefore must be better understood and incorporated into operations management practices. By integrating HRM and OM, companies can develop more effective strategies to improve both employee well-being and business performance, ultimately gaining a competitive edge in an increasingly complex and demanding market. Therefore, this study investigates how employee satisfaction influences business performance through various factors in private and public institutions across Cameroon. The findings will help to better understand how employee satisfaction in institutions and companies influences business performance.

Materials and Methods

Cameroon is a lower-middle-income country with a population of about 30 million people according to the recent World Bank database (<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL?locations=CM>). Located along the Atlantic Ocean, it shares its borders with the Central African Republic, Chad, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, and Nigeria. Cameroon is endowed with rich natural resources, including oil and gas, mineral ores, high-value species of timber, and agricultural products thereby providing raw materials for various industries. **Figure 1** shows the geographical location of Cameroon.

Figure 1. The geographical location and important cities in Cameroon.

Data collection

This study employed a survey technique of data collection, where a questionnaire was distributed to employees of various institutions and companies. In this regard, a survey was conducted targeting employees from various industries using questionnaire. It should however be noted that Cameroon is a bilingual country, where two languages (French and English) are spoken. In order to capture a significant number of respondents, two questionnaires with French and English languages questionnaires were designed. The responses from the two questionnaires were combined for the analysis. The study adopted factors that affect employee satisfaction hence business performance from several previous studies (Chi and Gursoy, 2009; Gazi et al., 2024; Jing, 2018; Jyoti and Sharma, 2012; Mafini and Pooe, 2013; Mwesigwa et al, 2020; Wu, 2024). Figure 2 presents the diagrammatic representation of the factors investigated and its relation with employee and business outcome.

Figure 2. Diagrammatic representation for all of the factors used in the study.

Statistical analysis

The study used descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum in summarizing and interpreting the dataset. The mean provides a central tendency measure for each factor, such as job satisfaction, work environment, and business performance, allowing us to understand the average response levels. For example, if the mean of Job Satisfaction is higher than the average values, it indicates that, on average, employees are slightly above neutral in their satisfaction. This helps identify areas where satisfaction levels are high or low, guiding potential interventions. The standard deviation measures the variability of responses, indicating how consistently employees feel

about each factor. A low standard deviation suggests that employees generally agree on the company's performance, while a high standard deviation might reveal diverse opinions, signalling a need for targeted improvements. The minimum and maximum values provide the range of responses, highlighting extremes in employee perceptions. For instance, if the minimum value is much lower, it indicates that some employees are highly dissatisfied, while a high maximum value shows good performance of the institutions. Together, these statistics offer a comprehensive understanding of employee satisfaction and its potential impact on business performance, enabling decision-makers to prioritize areas for improvement and leverage strengths to enhance overall company outcomes.

Correlation analysis

The correlation analysis was employed to investigate the relationship between human satisfaction on business performance. Correlation was used to understand how business performance is related to the independent variable (influencing factors) as well as relationship amongst the influencing factors. The correlation analysis is represented as:

$$r = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (1)$$

Where x_i and y_i are the individual factors, \bar{x} and \bar{y} are the means of the individual factors. Correlation varies between -1 and 1 where -1 implies perfect negative relationship while 1 implies perfect positive relationship. In this study, correlation is visualized using the correlation matrix.

Regression analysis

The regression analysis was used to investigate the overall response to the influencing factors. The general multiple regression model used in this study is represented as:

$$y = \beta_1 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

where y is the dependent variable (business performance), X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n are the independent variables or the influencing factors. β_1 is the constant term (or intercept) while $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n$ are the regression coefficient and ε is the error term. The regression coefficient β is calculated using the following expression:

$$\beta = (X^T X)^{-1} X^T y \quad (3)$$

where X is the matrix of the independent variables, y is the vector of the dependent variable and X^T is the transpose of X . $(X^T X)^{-1}$ is the inverse of matrix $X^T X$.

The above calculation uses the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique which minimizes the sum of squared residuals (SSR) to estimate the coefficients. SSR is denoted as:

$$SSR = \sum_{i=1}^n (y - \hat{y})^2 \quad (4)$$

Where y is the observed value and \hat{y} is the predicted value of the general regression model (equation 2). The negative values of β imply negative response while positive value implies positive response to the change of the influencing factors. Statistical significance was tested at 0.05 (95%) significance level.

Grey Relation Analysis

In addition to the regression models, this study used the Grey Relation Analysis (GRA) to identify the most influencing factors based on their impact. GRA was proposed by Deng, 1995 in early 1980s. It has gone through several modifications such as by Javed et al. (2022) and Quali. (2022) in order to improve its performance. GRA has recently been used in several studies such as Matambo. (2023) and Ivanova. (2022) in different environments. To rank the factors of employee satisfaction on business performance using GRA method, we first normalized the data between 0 and 1 ([0,1]). Normalization allows all the variables to be on the same scale, allowing a fair comparison with the target variable, business performance in this scale. We used the higher the better criterion (reference) to normalize the data, which is expressed as:

$$\varphi = \frac{x_i - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)} \quad (5)$$

Where x_i is the original value, $\min(x)$ is the minimum value and $\max(x)$ is the maximum value in the data. After normalizing the data, the Grey Relation Coefficient (GRC) is then calculated. Firstly, the absolute difference between each factor and the target variable (business performance) is computed as:

$$\nabla_i = |X_i - y| \quad (6)$$

Where X_i is the normalized value of the i th factor, calculated from the equation 5.

y is the normalized value of the target variable (business performance). Secondly, maximum and minimum difference is calculated across all the variables. Thereafter, GRC is calculated using the following expression:

$$GRC = \frac{\nabla_{\min} + \rho \cdot \nabla_{\max}}{\Delta_i + \rho \cdot \nabla_{\max}} \quad (7)$$

∇_{\min} and ∇_{\max} are the minimum and maximum differences across the variables respectively while Δ_i is the absolute

difference. The higher the GRC value, the high the impact on business performance. The above method has been recently used in several studies to determine and rank how different factors impact the business performances. All the calculations and plots in this study were performed using Microsoft excel, Origin lab and Python.

Results and Discussions

Overview of the data collected

Table 1 The statistical summary of the individual factors used in the study

Total responses	95				
Male	60				
Female	35				
Government institutions	61				
Private institutions	37				
Variable	Factor number	mean	std	max	min
Job Satisfaction	Factor 1	4.000	0.930	5	1
Work Environment	Factor 2	4.213	0.905	5	1
Compensation and Benefits	Factor 3	3.907	1.535	5	0
Recognition	Factor 4	3.560	1.368	5	0
Motivation	Factor 5	3.707	1.323	5	0
Feedback Frequency	Factor 6	3.840	1.577	5	1
Alignment with Career Goals	Factor 7	3.800	1.230	5	1
Communication and Culture	Factor 8	3.360	0.849	4	0
Team Collaboration	Factor 9	3.960	1.156	5	1
Personal Values	Factor 10	0.440	1.068	3	0
Supervisor Support	Factor 11	3.493	0.760	4	0
Leadership Transparency	Factor 12	0.600	1.208	3	0
Leadership Effectiveness	Factor 13	0.080	0.487	3	0
Daily Engagement	Factor 14	3.760	1.334	5	0
Long-term Commitment	Factor 15	0.240	0.819	3	0
Likelihood to Recommend	Factor 16	2.760	2.376	5	0
Training and Development	Factor 17	4.027	1.241	5	0
Resources for Skill Improvement	Factor 18	4.120	1.273	5	0
Importance for Business Outcomes	Factor 19	4.587	0.902	5	0

Table 1 presents the statistical summary of the factors used in the analysis. A total of 95 respondents (samples) were analysed of which 63% were males and 40% were females. Mean represents the average response of the respondents based the answers which varied between 0 and 5 for most of the questions. For instance, Job Satisfaction has a mean of 4, meaning most of the responses were cantered around option 4 for this factor. The standard deviation (std) indicates the dispersion of the responses for the factor. compensation and benefits show high std as compared working environment, indicating compensation and benefits were more spread. Minimum and maximum represent the lowest and largest values observed in each factor. For instance, job satisfaction has maximum of 5 implying that one response had highest score of 5. The above statistics help to understand whether the responses consistent or not during the survey. The higher the consistence, the higher the reliability of the information gathered from the respondents. It also implies that the factor is well understood or uniformly experienced by the respondents. Furthermore, the low variability and central tendency make easier to predict the outcomes or generalise the findings. This study observed both high and low variability in responses. For instance, working environment had lowest std (0.90) while mean of 4.21 indicating that most of the respondents agreed on the importance of work environment or rating of this factor on how it affects the employee satisfaction. On the other hand, compensation and benefits had high std and a mean of 3.91 indicating that may have different levels of importance or relevance to respondents.

Figure 3. Correlation among the factors influencing human satisfaction and impact of business performance.

Correlation among the factors presented in Figure 3 revealed both positive and negative correlations which implies the existence of negative and positive relationship among the variables and business performance. The correlation matrix reveals complex relationships among factors influencing employee satisfaction and their potential impact on business performance. Strong positive correlations, such as between Factor1(job satisfaction) and working environment (Factor 2) (0.58), collaboration and Factor10 (Personal Values) (0.61), indicate that these factors are closely interconnected. For instance, improvements in the workplace environment and collaboration with other companies are likely associated with higher job satisfaction. These strong relationships suggest that enhancing one factor can positively influence the other, creating a synergistic effect that boosts overall employee satisfaction and business performance. Moderate positive correlations, such as between benefits and recognition (0.48) or leadership transparency and Factor 15 (Commitment) (0.48), further highlight meaningful but less pronounced relationships, implying that targeted improvements in areas like (Factor 3) compensation and benefits or (Factor 12) leadership transparency can contribute to better outcomes, though not as significantly as strongly correlated factors.

On the other hand, weak or negligible correlations, such as between job satisfaction and supervisor support or leadership effectiveness and Factor 14 (daily engagement), suggest that some factors operate independently. For example, job satisfaction and supervisor support (Factor 11) show unrelated associations, indicating that changes in one may not affect the other. Negative correlations, such as between supervisor support and leadership transparency (-0.32) or likelihood to recommend and Factor 17 (training and development) (-0.35), reveal potential trade-offs, such as financial incentives possibly reducing the emphasis on recognition programs or excessive workloads diminishing employee engagement. These findings underscore the importance of a balanced and holistic approach to improving employee satisfaction, as focusing solely on one factor may not yield the desired results. By leveraging strong correlations, addressing trade-offs, and targeting independent factors with specific strategies, companies can create a more satisfied workforce, ultimately driving better business performance.

Model performance on understanding employ satisfaction on business performance

Table 2. Statistical summary on employ satisfaction on business performance using multiple linear regression model.

Adj. R-squared:	0.439
F-statistic:	4.221
Prob (F-statistic):	<0.01

The analysis based on the multiple linear regression model as shown in Table 2, on the relationship between employee satisfaction and business performance, yields meaningful insights. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.44 indicates that approximately 43.9% of the variability in business performance is explained by the independent variables. This suggests a moderate level of explanatory power, highlighting that employee satisfaction plays a significant role in influencing business outcomes. However, the remaining 56.1% of unexplained variability implies that other factors not included in the model, such as market conditions, leadership quality, or operational efficiency also influence business performance.

The F-statistic of 4.22 and its associated p-value being less than 0.01 confirm that the model is statistically significant, meaning the relationship between employee satisfaction and business performance is not due to random chance. This supports the validity of the model and its findings in this study. Despite this significance, the moderate adjusted R-squared and F-statistic values suggest that while employee satisfaction is an important predictor, it is not the sole driver of business performance. Companies should consider employee satisfaction as a key factor in their strategic planning but also recognize the need to address other variables to fully optimize business outcomes. Future research could explore additional predictors or refine the model to improve its explanatory power and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing business performance.

Individual influence of each of the variables on employ on business performance

The regression results for the individual factors provide a better understanding of how different factors can influence employee satisfaction hence impact on business performance. It can be noted from Table 3 that Factors such as work environment and job satisfaction have high regression coefficient values indicating a strong influence from these factors. This relationship is statistically significant, as evidenced by the t-statistic of 3.35 and a p-value of <0.01, suggesting that plays a meaningful role in driving business performance. Factors such as benefits and recognition have coefficients close to zero (-0.04 and 0.08, respectively) and are not statistically significant (p-values of 0.63 and 0.37 respectively), suggesting that these factors have little to no impact on business performance. Similarly, motivation and feedback from employers exhibit negative coefficients (-0.12 and -0.15, respectively), but only feedback from employers is statistically significant (p = 0.04), implying that it has strong negative influence on business performance.

On the other hand, collaboration and personal values have positive coefficients (0.21 and 0.04, respectively), but neither is statistically significant (p-values of 0.19 and 0.70), indicating that their influence on business performance is uncertain. Supervisor support and likelihood to recommend show positive coefficients (0.18 and 0.19, respectively) and are marginally significant (p-values of 0.05 and 0.09), suggesting they may have a modest positive influence on business performance. Training and development have a small but statistically significant positive coefficient (0.09, p = 0.04), indicating that this factor contributes positively to business outcomes. Factor 19 which represents business outcomes such as profits, stands out with a relatively large coefficient of 0.35 and a highly significant p-value of <0.01, highlighting its strong positive impact on business performance. Factors such as leadership transparency, leadership effectiveness, daily engagement, commitment, and Factor 18 (Skills) have coefficients that are either close to zero or not statistically significant, implying that they do not play a substantial role in influencing business performance.

Table 3 Individual impact of each factor on business performance. Coef is the correlation coefficient, std err is the standard error while t is the t statistic and P>|t| is the probability test." * represents significance at 0.05 (95% confidence level) significant level while *(99%) represents significance at 0.01(99% confidence level) significance level test.

	Coef	std err	t
Factor1	0.4111**	0.123	3.349
Factor2	-0.471**	0.14	-3.354
Factor3	-0.0347	0.071	-0.486
Factor4	0.0766	0.084	0.917
Factor5	-0.1156	0.073	-1.58
Factor6	-0.1433*	0.069	-2.085
Factor7	0.0215	0.083	0.258
Factor9	0.2051	0.153	1.338
Factor10	0.0402	0.105	0.383
Factor11	0.1839	0.095	1.94
Factor12	0.0822	0.166	0.495
Factor13	-0.0843	0.075	-1.119
Factor14	-0.1907	0.18	-1.061
Factor15	0.1184	0.075	1.59
Factor16	0.1898	0.113	1.677
Factor17	0.0893*	0.044	2.021
Factor18	0.0448	0.09	0.499
Factor19	0.3496**	0.083	4.218

The overall results suggest that some factors, such as job satisfaction and business outcomes, have a strong and significant positive impact on business performance, while others, like work environment and feedback from employers,

may have complex effect. Factors with insignificant coefficients, such as benefits and recognition, and career goals, appear to have little influence. These findings highlight the importance of prioritizing factors that significantly impact business performance, such as job satisfaction and outcomes, while addressing potential detractors like working environment and having feedback from the employees. Additionally, the marginally significant factors, such as supervisor support and likelihood to recommend, warrant further investigation to better understand their role in driving business outcomes. By focusing on the most influential factors, companies can develop targeted strategies to enhance employee satisfaction and, in turn, improve business performance.

Figure 4. Factor impact ranking using the grey relation coefficient (GRC).

The results from the Grey Relation Analysis (GRA) provide valuable insights into the relative importance of different factors influencing business performance. The analysis yields a Grey Relation Coefficient for each factor, which indicates the strength of its relationship with business performance. The higher the coefficient, the stronger the impact of that factor on performance. In this analysis, training and development emerge as the most influential, with a coefficient of 0.88, suggesting that it has the strongest relationship with business performance. This means that changes or improvements in training and development are likely to yield the greatest positive effect on the business. Business outcomes, with a coefficient of 0.86, follows closely behind, indicating a similarly significant role in shaping performance. These top-ranked factors should be prioritized for any interventions aimed at enhancing business results. Other factors such as personal skills and leadership transparency also demonstrated a strong relationship with business performance, though their impact is somewhat less pronounced than the top-ranked ones. These factors occupy the middle range of the ranking, suggesting they also deserve attention but perhaps not as significant as the highest-ranking variables. On the lower end, factors such as motivation show weaker relationship with business performance, reflecting a more modest influence on outcomes. While these factors should still be monitored, their lower Grey Relation Coefficients indicate that changes in these areas may not have as large an effect on performance as the higher-ranked factors. The GRA results provide a clear hierarchy of factors based on their impact on business performance. Training and business outcomes such as profits, stand out as the most critical variables, and efforts to optimize these factors are likely to yield the most significant improvements. Meanwhile, factors ranked lower, such as motivation, should still be considered in decision-making but may not be as pivotal in driving overall performance gains. This ranking allows businesses to focus their resources on the areas that will have the most substantial impact, ultimately contributing to more efficient and targeted strategies for performance enhancement across companies and institutions.

Conclusion

This study has explored the impact of employee satisfaction on business performance within Cameroon, using a comprehensive analysis of various factors influencing employee satisfaction. The results indicate that employee satisfaction plays a significant role in shaping business performance, with certain factors such as working environment, job security, and career growth opportunities showing strong positive correlations with business outcomes. Notably, the regression analysis highlighted that improvements in these key factors are likely to enhance business performance, while certain aspects, such as financial incentives and recognition programs, may exhibit more complex relationships or even negative effects in some instances. The findings also emphasize the importance of a balanced approach to employee satisfaction, where companies should prioritize factors that show the most significant influence on business performance, such as the working environment and career advancement opportunities, while addressing trade-offs or potential drawbacks in other areas like financial incentives. The Grey Relation Analysis (GRA) further reinforced these results, ranking factors such as training and development among the top drivers of business outcomes. This study concludes

that for institutions in Cameroon, a strategic focus on improving the key determinants of employee satisfaction, particularly those with the strongest impact on business performance, can lead to enhanced employee morale, productivity, and overall business success. Future research should focus on refining these findings by exploring additional variables or regional differences to gain a deeper understanding of how various factors interact and influence business performance.

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